

Edge intelligence secure frameworks: Current state and future challenges

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 12 August 2022

Revised 19 December 2022

Accepted 25 April 2023

Available online 28 April 2023

Keywords:

Edge computing

Edge intelligence

Artificial intelligence on edge

AI On edge

Distributed AI

Green computing

Security paradigm

ABSTRACT

At the confluence of two great paradigms such as Edge Computing and Artificial Intelligence, Edge Intelligence arises. This new concept is about the smart exploitation of Edge Computing by bringing together reasoning and learning by Artificial Intelligence algorithms and the sensors/actuators computing capabilities. Security is the third paradigm that must join the team in order to have resilient and reliable systems to be used in real-world applications and use cases. Hence, smartness is, in this context, a puzzle of several independent pieces which, once fitted, can derive unprecedented benefits: a) security, b) low communication latency and network load, c) cost and energy saving and d) scalability by means of resource virtualization close to the IoT data generators (IoT devices). In fact, by paying exclusive attention to some of those main pillars and, therefore, disregarding others, edge computation once in operation often suffers from bad performance, unforeseen events or does not exploit the enormous potential that should be unlocked if a proper and complete specification had been laid down. With all this in mind, this work provides a technical review of the available and up-to-date frameworks to implement secure Edge Intelligence, pinpoints the most relevant unfilled gaps (strengths and weaknesses) and, last but not least, includes challenges and future research lines as a result of our exploration.

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1. Introduction

Data generation has undergone an explosion during the last decade: the world is becoming increasingly connected. In fact, 29 billion of connected devices on the global network was estimated by 2022, according to the Telecommunications Industry Association, being more than half (18 billion) IoT devices [Telecommunications Industry Association \(2021\)](#). Enablers such as the Big Data paradigm or 5G mobile networks have paved the way towards a massive information sharing among countless geographically distributed systems and IoT devices such as wearable devices, mobile phones or computers. The deployment of sensors or IoT devices in industrial, biomedical or Smart City sectors along with the massive use of mobile phones has fostered not only this unprecedented data capture, but also the growth of more and more sophisticated algorithmic schemes capable of extracting knowledge

and giving value. And this is the rationale of Artificial Intelligence, hereinafter referred to as AI: building smart machines capable of mimicking human behaviour in the decision-making and performing tasks that typically call for human interaction.

In this context, two computing major paradigms arise: Edge Computing (EC), distributed computing aiming to bring the analysis of the collected information as close as possible to the devices in charge of this process; and Fog Computing, a decentralized computing structure located between the cloud and data-generator devices. Both approaches share some great challenges: privacy (sending sensitive data has blocked or hindered its use), latency (traditional schemes, where data was sent directly to the cloud, take considerable time hence causing usually severe bottlenecks in the processing procedures), scalability (the number of connected devices increases the cost of contracted services as well as transfer times) and the computational cost for unduly time-consuming algorithmic training processes.

In fact, the vast majority of real-world applications demands real-time processing capabilities locally on a hardware device. The self-driving car and robots in industry are some of the representative cases. However, it is necessary to distinguish **Inference at the Edge** versus **Training at the Edge**. Traditionally, the training

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stage was delegated to cloud services or private servers that were in charge of centralizing all the data to run the learning in private systems. Later, either obtained models were deployed on a device to perform inference functions (thus providing actionable intelligence) or the cloud service was in charge of the decisions and actions whereas the devices played the mere information collector role. Nevertheless, this approach has proved inadequate in non-stationary environments where the value of the data is strictly related to the time that elapses until their exploitation, hence being subject to obsolescence on account of the device-to-cloud transfer operation. Therefore, considering new distributed computing schemes is imperative, allowing for knowledge evolution and even the acquisition of ever more complex skills on the devices themselves. The intersection of these new computing paradigms with Artificial Intelligence technologies, especially deep learning models, have created a new inter-discipline, Edge AI or Edge Intelligence (EI) [Deng et al. \(2020\)](#).

On this basis, EI is expected to cover the real time operations including data collection and preprocessing, decision-making and action performance within admissible times, thence bypassing the need for a distant datacenter. Training at the edge aims to alleviate all the inefficiencies associated with a distributed architecture in addition to respecting the privacy of information. However, it faces a great challenge under the premises of constrained computational resources (memory, CPU, power or bandwidth) such as mobiles, embedded devices or FPGAs: how to develop advanced Deep Learning models and not die trying. And the deeper the model is probably the more accurate, but also the more intractable and slower in the training stage. This is even more worrying if the algorithm life cycle itself requires recurrent training phases (Online Learning or Incremental Learning).

The main advantages of the EC paradigm could be summarised into four following aspects:

- **Security:** The most famous promoter in EI have been the privacy and security concerns caused by the cloud computing and the appearance of plenty of resources composing the IoT “network”. Making security the kingpin forces the designers to take into account privacy-preservation requirements when developing all the policies and rules to be embedded into each of the edge device, despite being as close as possible to the “birth” of the data.
- **Cost and energy saving:** One important motivation for EI is reduce the energy footprint of our data society by transferring computing tasks to the edge devices. In this setting, Green Computing refers to the efficient use of computing resources with a focus on sustainability. Thus, by considering the environmental impact, Green Computing is moving towards the intelligent use of resources that minimizes the energy consumption and the waste of electronic devices. In this context, it is well known that centralized datacenters are one of the biggest carbon emitters in the world. In fact, according to [F. \(2021\)](#) forecast, the data center electricity need was of 286 TWh in 2016 and it will grow up to 321 TWh in 2030 if all currently known growth factors remain the same. As stated by the International Energy Agency, they are contributing to 0.3% of all global CO2 emissions. Cutting unnecessary traffic freeing up bandwidth and reducing storage and computation is the first step towards climate awareness. The analysis of the flow of data through networks and its optimization in efficient computing workloads are priority tasks to reduce the energy consumption related to the transport of data.
- **Latency:** Due to the proximity between the source and the consumer of the data (unlike the cloud computing paradigm), the time taken for data transmission is dramatically reduced. Im-

proving latency is indeed critical in the definition of an EC architecture.

- **Scalability:** Another valuable characteristic in EI is its nimbleness when it comes to adaptation to more and more computationally expensive environments. Traditionally, businesses which forecast growth and subsequent increasing computing needs tended to scale operations by resorting to the cloud whereas these days the proliferation of edge devices with extraordinary processing capabilities is making EC more attractive. Hybrid TI approaches, through negotiators and orchestrators, combine the consistency (as a controller) and immense power of the cloud servers and the agility of EC to cope with the challenging business needs. Which is incontestable is that scalability in IT infrastructure requires a redesign of the workload and analysis of both the performance and the effect of such upgrade on cost.

An inefficient definition or analysis of the aforesaid aspects can give rise to network overload, end-to-end latency, single point of failure or high power consumption among others, what prevents the correct productification of artificial intelligence and the capitalization of new market opportunities. In this context, the aim of this work is to bring together and integrate the various perspectives, coming from particular technological fields such as Security, Big Data, or AI, that apply to EI and give a comprehensive multidisciplinary view of the field.

On this basis, this paper contributions can be summarized in the following main points:

- Give an **extensive overview of the state-of-the-art of EI**, the enablers pushing forward the advances (i.e. technologies and frameworks) and the main challenges to be faced in its adoption.
- Include a detailed analysis of the **security perspective** focusing on the state-of-the-art enablers to deal with confidentiality, integrity, and availability EI issues, now that attack surface is even larger.
- Analyse the **role of AI in EC** not only from the perspective of AI executed or implemented in edge (AI on edge) but also from the contribution of AI for assisting the orchestration and operation of optimized edges (AI for edge). As for the former, the paper also lists the key technical aspects and requirements of AI on edge and gathers the main technical proposals presented by the community.
- Provide a comprehensive and in-depth review and comparisons between **schemes for EI implementation**, identifying various levels of abstraction: reference architectures (comprising even those less known proposals coming from the Reinforcement Learning field), implementations packaged in libraries and methodologies for operationalization.
- Present the **challenges and conclusions** in a prescriptive way to envision the future of this field.

In summary, the desired contributions in this survey can be summarized as follows: understanding the opportunities that are currently emerging in the EI field, especially analyzing the security dimension, to analyze which are the best architectures and frameworks that can help to adopt these technologies and have a clear idea of what are the current and future areas in which their benefits can be implemented or adopted.

Accordingly, the rest of the paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) gravitates on background of EI to later deep on this discipline in [Section 3](#), thoroughly analyzing the following points: a) main application problems and techniques, b) crucial technologies to deploy analytical processes at the edge and c) the security perspective. In [Section 4](#) the contribution will focus on describing the reference framework for AI secure computing environments at the

Fig. 1. EC paradigm.

edge, also evaluating the main frameworks or technologies existing today. Finally, the Section 5 presents the main challenges and problems to overcome in the EI discipline so that the materialization of its benefits in productive analytical processes becomes a reality.

2. Edge computing (EC)

As it has been introduced, the success of the Internet of Things and rich cloud services have helped create the need for EC, in which data processing occurs in part at the network edge, rather than completely in the cloud Cao et al. (2020).

Traditionally, analytical processes have been developed on Cloud Computing platforms. However, the centralized provisioning models in the cloud do not allow reaching quality levels in requirements such as latency, network traffic congestion or the use of resources, among others, mainly due to:

- Network congestion due to large volume of traffic.
- Less tolerance to failure and potential bottlenecks due to the centralization of processes and storage.
- High delays and latency due to the need for transmission to central nodes.
- Under-utilization of device resources in the nodes

To overcome these obstacles, the importance of EC, in which computing and storage nodes are placed at the Internet's edge in close proximity to mobile devices or sensors, have grown dramatically in recent years. Therefore, today, we find three computing approaches when it comes to solving real-world use cases with different requirements associated with processing and their infrastructure, so-called computing paradigms, that can be seen in the Fig. 1.

- Cloud computing understood as a paradigm that allows computing services to be offered through a network, which is usually the internet.
- EC understood as a distributed computing paradigm that brings computing and data storage to the location where it is needed to improve response times and save bandwidth.
- Hybrid approaches that allow for a mixture of the characteristics of both, thus getting the best of both worlds.

In this section we are centered on how EC is changing the “passive” role of the devices and the factors that promote this transition: the increasingly reduced cost of devices and sensors, along with the supplemented power embedded in even the most modest devices.

As stated in previous works such as (Lin et al. (2017a), Ai et al. (2018)), the main characteristics and functionalities in reference to EC paradigm are the following:

1. Dense geographical distribution, referring to the fact that the location of the devices is mostly distributed in a well-delimited area bypassing the need for cross WAN networks.
2. Mobility support. As the number of mobile devices is rapidly growing, EC give support to mobility, by means of Locator ID Separation Protocol (LISP).
3. Location awareness allows the final users to access services from the edge layer closest to their physical location.
4. Proximity, understood as closeness to end users.
5. Latency. EC reduces the latency in accessing the services, due to the proximity to the final user.
6. Heterogeneity refers to the diversity of communication technologies involved in the edge service delivery.
7. Speed. EC offers clear advantages in response time for real-time approaches.

Featuring these characteristics, EC has propelled substantial advances in the technological implementation of problems that historically were difficult to efficiently address, like Smart Health Abdellatif et al. (2019); Hartmann et al. (2019); Singh and Chatterjee (2021), Smart Home Gupta et al. (2020); Trimananda et al. (2018); Yu et al. (2021), Smart Transportation Jaisimha et al. (2020); Lin et al. (2020a) or Smart Grids Samie et al. (2019). In addition, it is necessary to highlight that the requirements and characteristics regarding security, which are a key point in this new EC programming model, are not included in these previous works, in contrast this article includes sections dedicated to their study and analysis.

In subsequent subsections, we delve into the reference architectures and main technologies engaged in this paradigm, see Section 2.1, and conclude with an overview of challenges posed by EC from the security perspective, Section 2.2.

2.1. EC Architecture and deployment modes

The origins of EC date back to the late 1990s where new networks were created to serve web and video content from servers deployed close to users Cao et al. (2020); Davis et al. (2004). At the beginning of the first decade of the 21st century, these networks evolved to host applications and components on edge servers, resulting in the first commercial EC services.

The stringent requirements coming from real use cases are widely diverse, giving rise to many deployment and multi-layered variants: “Fog”, “Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)” and “Cloudlets” Dolui and Datta (2017). The edge layer between the end device and the cloud will be implemented taking into account the intermediate nodes, the communication protocol, the network itself and the services provided by the edge layer.

- The “fog” provides a computing layer that uses instruments such as M2M gateways and wireless routers, called fog computing nodes, used to locally compute and store data from end-point devices before sending it to the cloud.
- Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), formerly Mobile Edge Computing, is a network architecture concept defined by ETSI that incorporates cloud computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of the cellular network and, more generally, on the edge of any network.
- The “cloudlet” concept, which without having own resources available at the edge of the radio access infrastructure, are virtualized resources for computing and storage integrated into the network operators' own infrastructures.

The EC paradigm supports a wide variety of end devices, applications, and use case scenarios. In order to determine the specific deployment variant able to cover the whole collection of requirements in the use case at hand, it is necessary to evaluate the application in detail and define a through strategy. This taxonomy and

decision framework has been presented in different articles, for example Pham et al. (2020) and the one previously cited Dolui and Datta (2017) in which the following parameters are considered: physical proximity, power consumption, computation time requisites, context awareness, logical proximity and non-ip support. This work focuses more on the possibilities of the MEC architecture to a wide variety of applications, where real-time response is imposed.

All these reviews are very useful work when facing general IT use cases, but not in the specific context of analytic EI applications, particularly if ensuring security and privacy settings are a must-have. In fact, the work proposed by Khan et al. (2019), states that breaches in security are likely to be present in those three types of deployment but it is rarely solved in an adequate way, being today a real challenge.

2.1.1. Virtualization technology

Virtualization should be a core strategy for EC right now. This technology allows to quickly and easily manage workloads, by switching between servers. Virtualization plays heterogeneous roles in many edge scenarios, including gateways or micro data centers that process data produced by sensors at the edge, or applications that run in containers or are hosted on virtual machines. In this context, the Modern EC paradigm has expanded significantly through virtualization technology.

There are numerous challenges in implementing EC, caused by the heterogeneity of the resources hosted on the edge and the requirements at the programming level (OS, language, versions, etc.), so a homogenization of them becomes a hard issue. virtualization enables the rise of this conceptualization. To materialize such conceptualization, two mechanisms are resorted to: virtual machines and containers. Nonetheless, the containers are the most disruptive technology which have been fostered by the edge paradigm. The keys to this technology revolution caused by containers lies in this statement: containerized applications can be anywhere, at any scale Barna et al. (2017).

2.2. Security as keystone technology

Nowadays, the number of application scenarios for EC paradigms is enormous. In fact, almost any aspect of our daily lives can be influenced by applications implemented in these infrastructures. However, without adequate security and privacy mechanisms, the benefits of these paradigms will be quickly eclipsed by the damage caused by malicious adversaries Roman et al. (2018), Atieh (2021). These new paradigms rely on new technologies, which also means an increment of the security risks. Several research reviews have been conducted on the security aspects of EC Husain et al. (2021), Zhang et al. (2018), Xiao et al. (2019), Caprolu et al. (2019), FC Alzoubi et al. (2021), Tange et al. (2020), Mukherjee et al. (2017), and MEC paradigms Ranaweera et al. (2021), Ali et al. (2021), Atiqur et al. (2020). A preliminary analysis of the threats affecting the availability, confidentiality and integrity of these paradigms is carried out in all of them, proposing an overview of the security mechanisms currently in place to protect both the involved actors and infrastructures. In addition, other security analyses have been carried out in specific areas, such as network security Weixiong et al. (2020), Yu et al. (2020), security in virtualisation techniques Flauzac et al. (2020), Sultan et al. (2019), De Lucia (2017) or forensic security analyses Math et al. (2021) in EC environments.

3. Artificial intelligence on/for edge

The complementarity between these disruptive technologies AI and EC can be studied from two perspectives:

Fig. 2. Different lines of technological specialization under EI perspective.

- Artificial intelligence on edge (see Section 3.1), focused on analyzing the possibilities offered by the edge devices to execute/implement different phases of the analytical processes life cycle, such as training or inference.
- Artificial Intelligence for edge (see Section 3.2), centered on how to take advantage of AI to provide processes with intelligent tools that assist at the deployment or use of the EC paradigm.

In both cases, the full portfolio of AI algorithmic techniques are available, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The whole spectra of AI-based techniques can be included into the following main division: **Optimization Intelligent, Machine Learning**, embracing **Deep Learning models**, and **Reinforcement Learning (RL)**, which can be defined as a hybrid algorithmic scheme lying in between of Optimization and Deep Learning, aiming at learning the optimum from exploration. The last but not the least, **Explainable AI (XAI)** as the set of tools and frameworks in charge of opening black-boxes (intricate models) to evaluate the algorithm performance on solid grounds and effectively support decision-making. All these intelligent tools, in order to be operationalized in real use cases, have to be designed with security in mind whatever the purpose: AI **on** the edge or AI **for** the edge.

A large part of the AI techniques to be applied to the edge must be distributed to adapt to the nature of this type of computing environment. It is important to highlight the two main challenges that occur in this type of distributed systems: first and foremost, the efficient parallelization of the training process and the creation of a coherent model, as mentioned in the work presented by Verbraeken et al. Verbraeken et al. (2020). The previously presented AI techniques will therefore need to be adapted to these new distribution requirements when working in EC environments. It is a subclassification of AI techniques called Distributed AI Nassef et al. (2022).

In this context, it is important to highlight the emerging Federated Machine Learning (hereinafter referred to as FL) techniques as an special and efficient casuistic of distributed techniques. FL is a distributed machine learning approach where multiple users collaboratively train a model, while keeping the raw data decentralized without being moved to a single server or data center Liu et al. (2022b)

3.1. Artificial intelligence on edge

AI on edge refers to the processing of one or multiple stages of Artificial Intelligence life cycle on edge, being the edge the environment in which the model has to be train, deploy or both.

In fact, the key question when considering an IE approach is: what is the role of the edge regarding the model (the most crucial part of the skeleton of the paradigm)? **“Training edge”** applies when the edge device is in charge of training its own model whereas **“Edge inference”** considers the edge devices as mere receivers of pre-trained models to act as inference engines.

To devise an effective strategy about how to deploy AI on edge in real-world settings, a helpful and practical guide is the one in-

Fig. 3. Different EI proportions and their respective attributes.

roduced by Zhou et al. (2019) which encourages practitioners to analyze the problem along with the environment constraints and requirements, such as latency, energy efficiency, privacy and WAN bandwidth cost, to set the most suitable ad-hoc configuration. Furthermore, Zhou et al. (2019) suggests a method to classify the degree of “intelligence” of such computing configurations, such as in Fig. 3 and analyzes the pros and cons of each alternative.

Some of those desirable characteristics (data offloading, transmission latency, WAN bandwidth cost, privacy, computational latency, and energy consumption) become the seed of new paradigms coined in the field of AI, such as:

- Real-time stream analytics** environments, where **latency and computational cost** are the key factors, it will be directed towards finding a solution close to the node, providing it with sufficient processing capacity. And both the training process and the inference process are of equal relevance Agrawal and Vulimiri (2017); Córdova (2015); Kejariwal et al. (2017); Milosevic et al. (2016); Verma et al. (2017); Yang et al. (2019a).
- Online learning and incremental learning** with recurring training phases, typically in **not stationary** environments where the data gradually changes over time. Key factors in this area of knowledge are: **energy consumption, path length of data offloading and bandwidth cost**. Many of the real-life examples respond to this casuistry, where sensors or machinery in general, due to the effect of degradation, to seasonality or periodicity effects, or to other agents, begin to record the data with slight variations Hoi et al. (2021); Losing et al. (2018); Pérez-Sánchez et al. (2018).
- Federated learning (FL)** appears on the scene to address **security and privacy** concerns in a context where the quantity and diversity of data, usually distributed among several companies or third parties, is a priority issue. The scheme relies on independent local training and a posterior aggregation of individual model parameters so as to build a global with a higher ability for generalization Lo et al. (2021); Yang et al. (2019b).

As for the training stage, and linked to this last novel paradigm, multiple devices can cooperate by means of two different training distribution approaches: a) the division of the training into processing chunks and planning of the execution of these parts between the different devices, or b) the parallel computation of the training in the devices and the necessary subsequent synchronization/aggregation of the results.

The second option is the pure distributed learning (multi-node ML) which may require specific treatments depending on the AI algorithm involved in the training, specially when it comes to the distribution/aggregation strategy of the results. The **aggregation topology** and **membership protocol**, which basically are targeted at the optimization of communications during edge training, do not only refer to the frequency nor to the aggregation mechanism, but also to policies about client selection, the management of associated problems -such as the appearance of “stragglers”-, or the instruments for the synchronism/asynchronism administration. The most typical aggregation topology alternatives are as follows:

- Single Point.** In distributed learning, the most common topology es a master-worker architecture, where a master node performs aggregation and the edge devices are the workers.
- Decentralized.** For example, by leveraging a blockchain-based consensus like in the work proposed by Li et al. (2020c), in which they present a decentralized federated learning framework based on blockchain, Without a centralized server, the framework uses blockchain for the global model storage and the local model update exchange. This approach will be adequately detailed in the section dedicated to security, see Section 3.3
- Gossip training.** The main idea is exchanging information peer-to-peer, assuring high scalability and privacy preservation. Called also epidemic protocol, it is a procedure based on the spreading epidemics or gossip phenomenon as metaphors for the way that data is expected to be disseminated to all members of a group. In Gossip learning Hegedús et al. (2019) the data stays at the edge devices, but it requires no aggregation server or any central component. There are no longer centralized nodes or “general/shared” variables. Fully asynchronous and decentralized, this approach has a direct impact on security/privacy.

Once decisions about model training distribution have been made, fine-grained technical questions came to the fore. Aiming at giving the reader a quick overview of some of the well-known strategies to adopt when designing EI schemes, the following structured list, according to the aforementioned requirements, is provided:

- Time response - Latency**
 - Partial Offloading:** The basis of this strategy lies in enabling the execution of applications or parts of code on mobile de-

vices with low latency thus improving the user experience [Ning et al. \(2018a\)](#); [Ren et al. \(2017\)](#).

- **Vertical Collaboration:** Vertical collaboration can be thought of as an “end cloud” strategy when edge architectures cannot afford the amount of AI queries by themselves, since they can share partial computation tasks and therefore guarantee the service of these queries. And also when the raw data should be pre-processed at the edge before they are streamed to the cloud [Gu et al. \(2022\)](#); [Wang et al. \(2018b\)](#).
 - **Horizontal Collaboration:** When all the AI tasks can be divided and assigned to multiple end devices or edge nodes to speed up AI computation by alleviating the resource cost [Gu et al. \(2022\)](#); [Wang et al. \(2018b\)](#).
 - **Conditional Computation Early Exit:** Since running DNNs can undermine the availability of resources at the edge and due to the fact that many instances call for less work to reach accuracy in the output, this technique adds several output branches at different levels which are activated when a defined criteria are met. Therefore, outcome from partial models is guaranteed, this being compliant with the requirements imposed. In the particular case of DNNs, these output branches are conceived as the layers composing the DNN itself. Some of the most recognised representatives of this technique are BranchyNet [Teerapittayanon et al. \(2016\)](#) and Edgent [Li et al. \(2018\)](#).
 - **Sharing AI Computation:** In order to improve the response time at the inference stage, one of the most resorted resource is cache and reuse previous results. Thus, redundant operations can be avoided and the latency is considerably reduced. Some examples in this regard can be found in Cachier [Droliá et al. \(2017\)](#), Glimpse [Chen et al. \(2015\)](#), DeepMon [Huynh et al. \(2017\)](#), DeepCache [Xu et al. \(2018\)](#) or any distributed RL architectures making use of shared replay buffers such as GORILA [Nair et al. \(2015\)](#), R2D2 [Kapturowski et al. \(2018\)](#) or Ape-X [Horgan et al. \(2018\)](#).
- **Constrained Devices**
- **Parameter pruning, gradient compression:** The large number of parameters to be learnt by an AI model, especially deep neural networks, causes a vast amount of energy consumption through the execution and optimization stages, plus communication latency in distributed training contexts. To overcome these limitations, multiple techniques, framed within Approximate Computing, have been proposed. Amongst them, parameter pruning, kernel filtering and gradient compression are the most representatives. In fact, Binarization and Quantization, also named as precision scaling, have gained a lot of attention in the last years as they lead to a reduction in memory and computational logic [Chen et al. \(2020\)](#); [Cheng et al. \(2018\)](#); [Lin et al. \(2017b\)](#); [Vogels et al. \(2019\)](#).
 - **Low-rank factorization:** It consists of removing redundant information by decomposing a complex model to a compact and approximate one with more lightweight layers. Singular Value Decomposition, Tucker decomposition and Block Term decomposition are the most employed methods [Swaminathan et al. \(2020\)](#).
 - **Improve acceleration by Optimizing DNN:** For an efficient DNN approximation at software and hardware levels, a specialized simulation environment and optimization methodology are required, to reduce execution and learning times, as well as to maximize energy savings [De la Parra et al. \(2020\)](#).
 - **Partitioning:** This strategy encompasses data, and/or model partitioning. In particular, with data partitioning we will achieve a logical distribution of large data sets in different partitions which can facilitate the management and im-

Fig. 4. Fields of application of AI in improving the operation of EI.

provement of the maintenance of the system [Mohammed et al. \(2020\)](#); [Zeng et al. \(2020\)](#).

3.2. Artificial intelligence for edge

The introduction of the EC paradigm in the development of analytical processes has resulted in great improvements and benefits, such as a better use of resources or an improvement in the latency of the response, to name a few. But it has also posed great challenges, especially in the operationalization stages, since the environment is more complex (distributed, limited, poor availability,) and the life cycle of the analytical processes has to be adapted.

There are new methodologies that focus on offering a set of recommendations to solve AI operationalization problems, such as MLOps [Ruf et al. \(2021\)](#). However, this practice does not yet contemplate distributed computing environments, for example in the context of EC, and therefore the frameworks and tools, such as MLFlow [Zaharia et al. \(2018\)](#) are not yet adequate for the operationalization of AI processes in EC environments. To cover this need, a research line interested in defining has recently arisen with works such as the one presented by Raj et al. [Raj et al. \(2021\)](#).

In this context, AI is once again playing a relevant role by providing intelligence for automation to the multiple tools that assist in the bunch of tasks that an analytical software life cycle must undertake, such as infrastructure provisioning, environment configuration, deployment and monitoring. Some examples can be currently found in the literature, like [Díaz-de Arcaya et al. \(2019\)](#) presenting a tool for optimizing the deployment of analytical pipelines in hybrid cloud/edge environments or the survey conducted by [Taherizadeh et al. \(2018\)](#) that collects works using AI techniques to carry out intelligent monitoring at the edge.

To illustrate the spectrum of possibilities of AI as a tool to enhance operation in EC environments, a possible taxonomy of the main AIOps-over-EI application fields is shown in [Fig. 4](#).

Regarding operation and following the categorization introduced in the work of Notaro et al. [Notaro et al. \(2020\)](#), we describe the challenges and the most recent advances in the EC paradigm:

- **Resource provisioning.** In resource provisioning for cloud computing, a relevant decision lies in how resources are allocated to meet the service level agreements (SLAs) of all applications to be deployed. In an EI environment, the challenges are mainly two: the analytical processes are computationally complex and difficult to optimize in processing time performance, and the EC paradigm causes a growing diversity in the type of resources to provisioning. Among all AI techniques, intelligent optimization has drawn special attention to estimate the need for resources

based on metrics of interest, such as infrastructure cost or user experience latency [Abouaomar et al. \(2021\)](#).

- Workload placement. Workloads can be desegregated and scheduled to be deployed into the most adequate resources according to metrics related to performance, costs, or security concerns. AI algorithms can be used to recommend a decomposition strategy and optimize the scheduling. There are several works that have analyzed the use of different algorithms or have proposed AI-based frameworks, for example the work of [Santoro et al. \(2017\)](#).
- Network use improvement. Particularly, the use of AI-powered 5G networks can greatly improve the EC paradigm in terms of latency and bandwidth utilization. A comprehensive survey in this AI application is the one conducted by [Fu et al. \(2018\)](#).
- Failure prediction. In computing systems, one fundamental cause of availability and performance degradation is the accumulation of anomalies of different nature which eventually leads to resource exhaustion. In such complex EC environments, it is essential to prevent these situations by making the environment resilient. Most of the proposed solutions are based on AI techniques in charge of foreseeing these failures. The challenge is again to adapt the numerous existing works, such as [Zhao et al. \(2019\)](#), to the new considerations and requirements of the EI paradigm.

In addition to the operationalization of processes, AI can provide benefits and intelligence in other aspects of EC, such as in the guarantee of complementary requirements including safety and green computing.

In the field of safe computing, there are numerous works that ensure privacy requirements compliance at the edge by means of AI techniques, such as [Moustafa \(2021\)](#) for smart cities or [Rajendran et al. \(2021\)](#) in the healthcare domain. Besides, EC has also been used for implementing anomalies [Preuveneers et al. \(2018\)](#) or intrusion [Liu et al. \(2022a\)](#) detection systems.

Finally, green computing, understood as the practice and procedures of using computing resources in an environment-friendly way while maintaining overall computing performance [Saha \(2018\)](#), has gained a lot of attention these years [Feng et al. \(2020\)](#); [Yang et al. \(2020\)](#). In fact, a novel paradigm has been coined: Green Edge Computing [Ning et al. \(2018b\)](#). The commonalities between green computing and EI are multiple. Obviously, both share the energy efficiency in the claim, which EI mainly tackles by the reduction of the data centralization consequently decreasing the need for data centers that consume huge amounts of energy. Last but not least, resource planning based on energy efficiency objectives and the reduction of data traffic may also contribute to a greener computation. AI optimization algorithms become a must-have to this end.

3.3. EI security perspective

Cybersecurity in the EI domain is essential to provide security features such as deterrent, prevention, and detection of cybercrimes through appropriate security controls [Yang et al. \(2021\)](#) [Li et al. \(2021\)](#) [Ansari et al. \(2020\)](#). EI covers a wide range of applicability domains, such as medicine, Industry 4.0, autonomous driving, etc, in which not only economic aspects but also human lives are at risk. The main objective of general cybersecurity is to ensure the CIA Triad: Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability [Reshan and Saleh \(2021\)](#) [Bhattacharjya \(2022\)](#).

Confidentiality refers to the information privacy. In the EI domain, it may refer to the input data applied to AI algorithms or the AI algorithms themselves. The information must be kept private at any time; this means in the three possible states of data:

- Data at rest refers to data (sensitive information or AI algorithms) housed physically on a physical data center, on a private or public cloud, or in a third party storage application. It is usually stored and protected by a firewall or antivirus software [Kamoun-Abid et al. \(2021\)](#). However, they do not guarantee safety from phishing or social engineering attacks as well as from insiders. For this reason, encryption is also needed to provide an additional layer of defence and prevent unauthorized users from accessing the information. Data is considered secure at rest when it is encrypted with a sufficiently long and random encryption key that is not stored on the same location [MOHAMMED and ABED \(2020\)](#) [Omar and Abed \(2020\)](#) [Husein et al. \(2020\)](#). Most of the NoSQL databases do not employ any technique to protect the data at rest; for example, MongoDB does not provide any method to encrypt data; it must be encrypted at the application layer before writing the data to the database [Singh \(2019\)](#). Neither ANSI SQL, SQL/MP nor SQL/MX does not have standards for encrypting data. Only a few provide encryption mechanisms, such as Cassandra, which uses TDE (Transparent Data Encryption) [Mukherjee \(2019\)](#).
- Data in motion also refers to data (sensitive information or AI algorithms) in transit; it is information transferred between different locations. The first consideration to avoid confidentiality issues in data in motion is to reduce data movement if possible. In this sense, FL solutions, in which data does not need to move, highly improve confidentiality [Yang et al. \(2019b\)](#) [Cirincione and Verma \(2019\)](#). Moreover, encrypted connections (SSL, HTTPS, FTPS, TLS, etc.) are usually considered for any kind of data transference [Rezaei and Liu \(2019\)](#). DLP (Data Loss Prevention) technologies may also help to protect data in motion by detecting and blocking attempts to send confidential data outside or to copy data to external storage systems, such as USB drives or cloud applications [Jadhav and Chawan \(2019\)](#).
- Data in use refers to data (sensitive information or AI algorithms) that is stored in memory or is being actively processed by computing equipment. Its privacy can be guaranteed by means of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) [Soykan et al. \(2022\)](#) [Novikova et al. \(2022\)](#), [Rao and Bertino \(2019\)](#) such as Differential Privacy (DP) [Wei et al. \(2020\)](#) [Seif et al. \(2020\)](#), Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [Yousuf et al. \(2021\)](#) [Rahman et al. \(2020\)](#) or Multiparty Computation (MPC) [Kanagavelu et al. \(2020\)](#) [Safari et al. \(2021\)](#), or other cryptography techniques [Lin et al. \(2020b\)](#). Additionally, secure hardware elements, such as Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) can protect data both at rest and in use [Zhenyu et al. \(2019\)](#) [Mo et al. \(2021\)](#).

Integrity is a fundamental aspect of data security and reliability. Software or hardware malfunctions as well as malicious intrusions may cause unexpected and unauthorized modifications to data. In general, the cryptographic techniques used to guarantee the confidentiality of the information also guarantee its integrity [Chen et al. \(2021\)](#) [Zamani et al. \(2021\)](#). Additionally, redundant information can be separately kept ensuring integrity by recomputing the redundant data from the actual data and comparing it with the stored redundant information [Kadekodi et al. \(2019\)](#). In this sense, mirroring techniques, in which two or more copies of the same data are separately kept, enable integrity checks by comparing the copies [Gallersdörfer et al. \(2021\)](#). Checksumming is also considered for performing integrity checks [Kim \(2021\)](#). Checksums are usually generated by a hash function as a data summary that can be persistently stored. Integrity can be then verified by comparing the stored and the newly computed values on every data read [Prasath \(2015\)](#). In this sense, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) has started to be widely considered for secure checksums storage due to its inherent security features such as information integrity [Truong et al. \(2019\)](#) [Rahalkar and Gujar \(2019\)](#).

Finally, availability may refer to information availability, guaranteeing its accessibility to authorized users or to system/service availability, guaranteeing the possibility of executing AI algorithms. In general, availability can be improved by means of redundancy, in other words, keeping the same information/service in different locations, and automatic failover techniques [Matani et al. \(2020\)](#) [Cheng et al. \(2021\)](#). Another simple step is to avoid Single Points of Failure (SPoF) typical of traditional centralised solutions by evolving to decentralized and/or distributed solutions, such as Blockchain [Shah et al. \(2020\)](#). Software-defined infrastructures are usually easier to move around and scale, improving availability [Benzekki et al. \(2016\)](#). Moreover, FL itself also increases EI availability as the AI models training is distributed among several participants.

3.3.1. Distributed learning security risks

AI and security have been developed in parallel, with different objectives, but deployed in combination. However, as discussed in the previous sections, the emergence of distributed learning brought about the parallelization of the training processes, focusing on improving efficiency and performance but without regard to security. Later on, the need was felt to provide extra security, especially in terms of privacy, and FL solutions came into play. FL means a new philosophy of secure by design EI, since privacy awareness is implicit in its design. FL can be then considered the basis for new secure EI frameworks. Although FL improves some aspects of the EI security, specially those related with the confidentiality, it is not free of risks. In general, FL systems add new inherent security risks [Mothukuri et al. \(2021\)](#) [N and P \(2021\)](#) to the risks already identified for EI.

- Risks associated to participants. There may be malicious participants (or even a compromised centralized server) in the federation who intend to deliberately damage the federation by poisoning [Tolpegin et al. \(2020\)](#) or byzantine attacks [Blanco-Justicia et al. \(2021\)](#). They may poison the local model before sending it to the centralized server or they may also try to insert a backdoor to the global model for directly corrupting it. By this way, the global model accuracy may be reduced, influencing the model to output wrong labels. It is difficult to avoid this risk, but advanced authentication and encryption techniques could highly reduce it [Ma et al. \(2021\)](#). Besides, new malicious participants identification techniques, such as federated leave-one-out (LOO), as well as participants rating techniques to avoid future malicious participations, such as Federated Shapley Value (SV), have started to be studied in the literature [Wang et al. \(2020b\)](#).
- Risks associated to models. In traditional approaches based on a centralized server for the aggregation, local model transference from the participants is needed. In this sense, data confidentiality is at risk as details about the data used for each local model training can be, in some cases, inferred from the model itself (gradient leakage) [Geiping et al. \(2020\)](#) [Jin et al. \(2021\)](#). In this scenario, advanced encryption techniques are also recommended, such as MPC, FHE or TEE for a confidential aggregation process [Kanagavelu et al. \(2020\)](#) [Fang and Qian \(2021\)](#). Besides, current distributed FL solutions also reduce the local models sharing among the participants [Samarakoon et al. \(2019\)](#).
- Risks associated to the traditionally centralized server. Centralized solutions mean SPoF and bottlenecks, highly reducing the scalability level of the overall solution. In this sense, different solutions based on decentralization have been proposed in the literature: distributed FL, the combination of FL with MPC [Kanagavelu et al. \(2020\)](#) or with DLT technologies [Kim et al. \(2018\)](#) [Qu et al. \(2020\)](#). By this way, the availability of the orchestrator and aggregator increases.

Fig. 5. Taxonomy of the main concepts when implementing EI.

- Risks associated to federation orchestration. Federation usually requires traceability and accountability of the participants in order to identify their real contribution to the global model (for the malicious participants detection, for the generation of rewards, etc.). In this sense, DLT technology has been widely used [Kim et al. \(2018\)](#) [Qu et al. \(2020\)](#).

4. Implementing EI: Architectures, frameworks and methodologies

In this section, we will review the state of the art in terms of useful tools to implement EI as a paradigm in between EC and AI usually developed under distributed learning schemes to improve performance, increase accuracy and facilitate scalability to AI-based services. This section will cover different levels of abstraction, as depicted in [Fig. 5](#): from the conceptualization of architectures to specific implementations packaged in libraries, plus methodologies for the operationalization.

Particularly, the section analyses existing frameworks in the different paradigms of EC, EI and distributed learning as can be seen in the center of the [Fig. 5](#). It is interesting to start with the reference architectures used as basis to build these frameworks (upper part of the [Fig. 5](#)) as well as the methodologies that can be applied to bring the resulting developments to productive environments (bottom part of the [Fig. 5](#)).

4.1. Conceptualization of reference architectures

Multiple architectures might be conceptualised for EI according to the requirements imposed for the intended usage and also depending on the AI technique for which they have been designed. When training is to be executed on edge, distributed learning architectures have to be leveraged. We discuss hereinafter the most renowned proposals in the literature: from the first born into the RL field, to the current and popular reference architecture for FL and going through numerous works in which ad-hoc conceptualizations have been made to solve specific problems.

The first one dates back to 2015, coined as GORILA in the RL discipline ([Fig. 6](#)). 2 years later, the democratization of distributed learning in the AI field led to the birth of FL architecture ([Fig. 7](#)), even though the procedure then described fell near A2C/A3C (2016) in RL.

[Fig. 8](#) details a generic and agnostic of the AI technique conceptualization for EI which collects all the necessary modules and components required to surpass the limitations pinpointed so far.

This proposed architecture has this functional arrangement:

- The cloud layer is composed of modules dedicated to basic AI or processing techniques and the necessary control to imple-

Fig. 6. First distributed learning architecture in RL (2015) Nair et al. (2015).

Fig. 7. FL proposed architecture (2016) Raza et al. (2022).

ment distributed processing and AI techniques, such as modules responsible for the control and monitoring of edge devices.

- The edge layer is in charge of: collection and centralization of data, security and AI processing at the local level.

4.2. Distributed learning frameworks

As stated in Section 3.1, a designer will opt for a distributed learning approach when needing scalability (concretely, the ability of the algorithm to learn from a big amount of data) or data protection (whether the information must remain private). Different goals will tip the scale towards either highly-efficient or security-aware frameworks.

The distribution does not necessarily imply that the solution is framed in an EC model, but it can be about parallelization between nodes or federation between geographically different repositories instead. The edge layer made up of physical devices does not have to be present in all solutions called DML - Distributed Machine Learning. Notwithstanding, it is important to consider solutions of this type because they have multiple functionalities and characteristics in common with distributed systems deployed in EC.

In order to compare the contributions of distributed learning state-of-the-art frameworks, the Table 1 collects the most recog-

nized frameworks in the literature along with their expected benefits, with special attention to those critic aspects of EI shown in Fig. 3, namely: data offloading, transmission latency, WAN bandwidth cost, computational latency, and energy consumption, besides the privacy aspect.

Generally, the more distributed the more communication latency. When it comes to RL, buffers contribute to a faster convergence (specially when adopting prioritized experience replay buffers) but requires a higher use of memory. Asynchrony, in turn, avoids waiting for stragglers in the training stage and, in consequence, waiting for collecting trajectories/experiences as well, which is, in fact, the most time-consuming task in RL. However, asynchrony is prone to induce more variance in the learning.

Whatever the framework, the aggregation management is one of the critical points in the conceptualization of distributed learning approaches since it impacts in the quality of many important aspects, such as latency or the computing efficiency. Several alternatives for aggregation can be adopted: adding policies for client selection [FedCS, FedSEL], adding a new layer to the NN to match and merge similar responses [FedPER, FedMA], defining various types of synchronous and asynchronous aggregations [FedAT], weighting the contribution of clients updates [FedAdp], among others.

As for FL-related frameworks, security/privacy becomes a must-have for which several strategies are applied: limiting the number and the size of communications [Safer], using secure protocols (MPC, among others) [Safer], employing one untrusted Cryptographic Service Provider [ESMFL], or giving a solution to the problem of untrustworthy devices [BlockFL].

4.3. Edge intelligence frameworks

In this section we introduce the frameworks that are generally used in the implementation of AI in the EC model, since they represent the technological baseline to advance in new smarter tools targeting more specialized applications in the context of EI.

The following Table 2 summarizes the main frameworks characteristics, analyzed under the different dimensions that were proposed in the work Ai et al. (2018) and discussed above.

As mentioned in the previous sections the scientific community is investing many resources in developing, describing and/or unifying criteria on the most effective way to deploy AI models on the edge, and proof of this are the following frameworks designed, precisely for that, to implement the ML and DL models according to the constraints placed from edge environments. Next, the main frameworks which were pioneers in trying to integrate the processing of analytical models in the EC paradigm are introduced.

Fig. 8. Secure EI reference architecture.

However, most of them are focused on specific aspects or functionalities and cannot be reused or provide a generalist solution to the EI paradigm.

- DeepX Lane et al. (2016) is a framework devised to control the edge devices. It automates various machines from industrial robots to heavy machinery to solve on-site problems in a wide range of industries.
- PipeDream is a Deep Neural Network (DNN) training system for GPUs that parallelizes computation by pipelining execution across multiple machines.
- Arden Wang et al. (2018a) is a cloud-based framework which splits the DNN across mobile phones Wang et al. (2018a).
- GAIA Hsieh et al. (2017), is a geo-distributed ML system that employs an intelligent communication mechanism over WANs to efficiently utilize the scarce WAN bandwidth, while retaining the accuracy and correctness guarantees of an ML algorithm.
- AdaDeep Liu et al. (2018) is a usage-driven, automated DNN compression framework for systematically exploring the desired trade-off between performance and resource constraints, for example in EC environments.
- Edgent Li et al. (2018) is a collaborative and on-demand DNN co-inference framework with device-edge synergy.
- Foggycache Guo et al. (2018) is a framework to implement the concept of cross-device approximate computation reuse.

As we have explained previously, all of them focus on NN and on different problems of their implementation on device networks, whether they are mobile or industrial devices. But none offers an EI holistic vision or the design of a generalist framework to implement EI solutions.

It is also interesting to name different frameworks and libraries dedicated to the implementation of FL techniques. In this context, the following open-source tools are available as software platforms

supporting AI and data analytics for EC: TensorFlow Federated¹, FATE² (Federated AI Technology Enabler), PaddleFL³ and Flower⁴. These libraries are stable developments, but oriented to very specific FL use cases, leaving many of the problems related to how to implement other AI techniques in EC environments untreated.

4.4. EI operationalization methodology: Approaches and tools

In this last section we try to analyze a group of resources or tools less studied, this means those technologies in charge of materializing an operationalization methodology for IE: automatization, scale/speed up or enable the deployment of analytical processes at the edge.

In previous sections we have mentioned new paradigms and operations such as AIOps or MLOps and stated, after a deep analysis of the literature, that in all these initiatives there is no dimension including, among its functionalities, possible solutions to the problems that EC has to face or specific aspects dedicated to EI. In this context, however, we have found several articles that may set the foundations for future research in this line.

The three main approaches to be highlighted are the following:

1. First of all, the notion of the EI paradigm as a service presented in the article Raith and Dustdar (2021), with fully available and configured environments that only need to be piloted for the use case.
2. The second work Casadei et al. (2022) focuses on the design of tools to orchestrate the deployment of analytical services at the edge based on their performance. Even though revolving around a very specific casuistry, it could be transferred to simi-

¹ Tensorflow Federated <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated>.

² <https://fate.fedai.org>.

³ PaddleFL <https://paddlefl.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>.

⁴ Flower <https://flower.dev>.

Table 1
Distributed learning related frameworks.

Framework	Year	Description	Main Contribution	Expected Benefits
GORILA Nair et al. (2015)	2015	Massive distributed architecture for RL	Distributed RL framework for multi-agent asynchronous learning with parameter server as Aggregation Manager	Faster learning due to the replay buffer in charge of letting agents share experiences.
A2C Grondman et al. (2012)	2016	Synchronous advantage actor critic framework	Synchronous learning divided into a Critic estimator for the value function and an Actor for determining the policy.	Improves stability in learning
A3C Mnih et al. (2016)	2016	Asynchronous advantage actor critic framework	Asynchronous learning based on A2C framework	Faster training
FedAvg McMahan et al. (2017)	2017	An Iterative model averaging FL Framework	FedAveraging algorithm for aggregation	Reduces communication cost by locally-computed updated aggregation.
IMPALA Espeholt et al. (2018)	2018	Scalable Distributed Deep-RL with Importance Weighted Actor-Learner Architectures	Asynchronous, similar to A3C but sending experiences to the learner and including importance sampling	Improves efficiency stability in learning.
R2D2 and Ape-X Kapturowski et al. (2018) Horgan et al. (2018)	2018	Asynchronous learning for distributed framework with prioritized experience replay	A synchronous framework with a replay buffer ranked according to the learning update	Faster learning convergence by means of the prioritized experience replay buffer, low latency communications.
Zoo Zhao et al. (2018)	2018	Composable Services to deploy of ML models locally on edge	Resources Optimization, ML as Services on edge devices.	Reduces latency in data processing, and minimises the raw data revealed.
FedPer Arivazhagan et al. (2019)	2019	Federated Learning with Personalization Layers	Models on the edge have common shared base layers and personalized ones.	Improves results with data heterogeneity (avoids degradation of performance coming from the standard federated averaging).
FedAsync Xie et al. (2019)	2019	Asynchronous federated optimization Framework	Asynchronous Training and Aggregation	Improves flexibility and scalability and tolerates staleness.
FedCS Nishio and Yonetani (2019)	2019	Client Selection for Federated Learning with Heterogeneous Resources	Aggregation Management: client selection	Improves performance, reduces training time.
BlockFL Kim et al. (2019)	2019	Blockchained Federated Architecture	Blockchain as orchestrator	Optimizes communication, computation and latency.
FedMa Wang et al. (2020a)	2020	Federated matched averaging algorithm for FL.	Adds a layer to match and merge similar responses	Improves accuracy, reduces communication cost.
FedAT Chai et al. (2020b)	2020	Synchronous intra-tier training and asynchronous cross-tier training	Weighted Aggregation Heuristic and Polyline-encoding-based compression algorithm	Improves accuracy, reduces communication cost.
Safer Beguier and Tramel (2020)	2020	A new protocol for secure aggregation in collaborative FL.	Model update compression to secure computation.	Secure aggregation with low communication cost.
Safa Wu et al. (2020)	2020	SAFA, a semi-asynchronous FL protocol	Model distribution, Aggregation Management: client selection	Improves round efficiency and convergence.
TiFL Chai et al. (2020a)	2020	A Tier-based FL System	An adaptive tier selection approach to mitigate the heterogeneity in resource and data. Aggregation Management: client selection	Improves round efficiency and convergence in heterogeneous conditions.
FEDXGB Liu et al. (2020b)	2020	HE for secure aggregation and regression tree of XGBoost	Forced Aggregation by HE and secret sharing, Federated Extreme Gradient Boosting	Robust against user dropout, reduces communication, preserves privacy.
SimFL Li et al. (2020a)	2020	Similarity based Horizontal FL	Weighted Gradient Boosting (Aggregation Management)	Reduces computation and communications
ESMFL Lin et al. (2020b)	2020	Efficient and Secure Models for FL	Optimization Architecture (Parameter Regularization, Weight Pruning), Sparse model	Reduces communication cost, secure and privacy-preserving
FedSel Liu et al. (2020a)	2020	Framework for federated SGD under Local Differential Privacy	Aggregation Management: client selection	Improves communication and computational cost, ensuring convergence and privacy.
FedSMB, FedMMB Nasirigerdeh et al. (2020)	2020	FedMMB decouples the batch size from the number of batches, performing multiple local updates in each round	Introduces Federated-centralized concordance	Improves accuracy and communication cost in Non-IID settings.
FedAdp Wu and Wang (2021)	2021	Fast-Convergent FL with Adaptive Weighting	Weighted Aggregation Management	Accelerate model convergence under Non-IID settings.

lar problems or translated into new deployment objectives such as edge layer reliability or green computing.

- Finally, the work [Miñón et al. \(2022\)](#) centers precisely on providing a framework that helps the operationalization of analytical processes taking into account the edge layer as one of the possible levels of computation. Its objective is to support the user through the semi-automated deployment of analytical pipelines in complex computing hybrid environments.

5. Challenges and futures lines in EI

As it has seen in the previous sections, EI today is a extensive range of many tools and schemes that provide the flexibility to design a system that meets a wide variety of needs imposed by very specific contexts and requirements. Nonetheless, this flexibility and the high demanding EI contexts, especially in relation to availability, require ever more exquisite solutions that are not without chal-

Table 2
Frameworks to implement AI at the edge level.

	Dense Distribution	Mobility	Location	Proximity	Latency	Heterogeneity	Speed	Security	Ref.
DeepX	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Lane et al. (2016)
PipeDream	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Harlap et al. (2018)
Arden	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Wang et al. (2018a)
Gaia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Hsieh et al. (2017)
Adadeep	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Liu et al. (2018)
Edgent	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Li et al. (2018)
Foggycache	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Guo et al. (2018)

Fig. 9. Challenges (1) and future research lines (2) in EI.

allenges to be addressed. Below are pinpointed the main challenges with the corresponding futures lines gaining attention these days. Those critical aspects of EI that we already described in Fig. 3 are highlighted in bold. A diagram is provided (Fig. 9) to outline the key concepts regarding these conclusions.

- **Agility:** data should be collected, processed and managed before it can be used by whatever analytic system Dautov et al. (2021). Data agility is related to how quickly some value can be extracted from a large amount of data in order to transform it into some action. Agile data management demands for near real-time data, a deep analysis about the **requirements** of the **network communications** and the **privacy**. This means the alignment of the needs of the problem with its architecture (Fig. 8).

In order to achieve the data agility, the overall workflow must be defined to determine the task partitioning policies, edge's side computation, node selection procedures and the operationalization/life-cycle management. All this must be in turn adjusted to comply with the scheduling, synchronization, and security strategies.

- **Reducing transmission latency:** Applying compression techniques to reduce the amount of data transmissions over a network has an instant impact on it and **increasing network bandwidth**. In this sense, there are two main types of data compression: lossless compression, and lossy compression. When working with sensitive data or critical IoT applications, lossless compression is the most recommendable setting, even at the expense of a higher compression ratio. Manifold works have proposed techniques for convolutional and fully connected

layers in neural networks, but recurrent layers have been less studied in spite of their popularity in the literature.

On the other hand, many works are being carried out with the aim of **reducing transmission latency**. Herein, the most promising methodology is quantization, intending to train a model by approximating float parameters with a set of discrete values (low precision calculations) without compromising accuracy. The best representative of this approach are the Binary Neural Networks, recently trained on Quantum Processing Units to get quantum speed-up Sasdelli and Chin (2021).

- **Naming:** On EC, due to the heterogeneity and number of the connected systems and the mobility challenges they have to address, an efficient mechanism of the naming scheme is vital, but at the moment there are no standards for it. In this context, a definition of dynamic network topology, privacy and security protection, as well as scalability are linked to its success. Cao et al. (2018)
- **Distributed computing:** Edge infrastructure must always be suited appropriately, but putting into practice computing on edge, by separating the applications into multiple elements corresponding to the resources, becomes essential. Besides, as has been pointed out throughout the article, FL is often employed when **privacy** conditions are required. The benefits of this decentralised approach are promising: a) a centralized server is not critic; b) security advantages, since the data remains in each of the nodes; c) real-time predictions locally computed, d) communications are not mandatory in the predictive process and e) large hardware infrastructure is not required. Among others, an essential pillar of FL and any approach within an EC environment is security. However it can introduce some other

open challenges such as: the trade-off between accuracy and network communications, deal with distributed imbalanced or biased datasets, latencies due to synchrony schemes or fully decentralized learning, amongst others [Kairouz et al. \(2019\)](#).

- **Scheduling strategies:** As long as EC can be deployed on a huge variety of heterogeneous platforms, the runtime and hardware resources of these nodes can differ from each other and the programmer must take into account their peculiarities. The scheduling strategies are needed to coordinate the mapping between the computing tasks and available edge resources. The goal is to optimize workload scheduling to run in the right place at the right time. Scheduling becomes even more arduous when taking into consideration some of the complex dynamics occurring at the edge and it is a prerequisite that these resources respond dynamically and in real time. An illustrative example is when the terminal devices move locations or service requirements vary; scenario in which getting the dynamic scheduling make coherent and consistent decisions is considerably challenging.
- **Security and accessibility:** Unlike cloud-based solutions, the edge environments lack security technologies and privacy protection mechanisms specifically designed for the current AI-based applications that the edge paradigm facilitates. For that reason, EC is not free of security risks, as those gathered in section 3.3. Furthermore, edge environments usually involve a considerable number of users, resulting in complex user access policies as well as advanced authentication and authorization systems [Li et al. \(2020b\)](#) for guaranteeing a correct access.
- **Data abstraction:** As data is a cornerstone of this conceptualization; data storage, data persistence and access must be aligned and managed, according to the existing data rules, into the new ecosystem composed of edge devices. The challenge arises mostly when finding solutions that consider and use the storage available at the edge and abstract the analyst or end user from having to know the real physical location of the data.
- **Edge control and management:** There are great difficulties in the control of edge layer devices, such as the heterogeneity in computing and storage characteristics, their connectivity or the large volume of devices to monitor at the same time. Nonetheless, the biggest challenge today is the mobility and device location. Since edge node location can be flexible, the procedures and protocols in charge of the node net management must be accordingly established, regardless of the physical edge location. Besides, the design of the management protocols must assure a safe and stable system, mainly focused on four considerations: differentiation, extensibility, isolation, and reliability (DEIR). Green Computing paradigm is nuclear for the emergence and promotion of sustainable EI. With the number of devices increasingly growing, as well as their sensing, computing and communications capacity, the bandwidth saturation and the energy limitations and associated costs will call for novel schemes, routines and actual awareness for sustainability. The scientific community is devoting a remarkable effort in Network Virtualization technologies to achieve an efficient deployment of edge devices. Two frameworks stand out in this line: [Liu et al. \(2019\)](#) proposes a detailed framework with MEC technology, where the main idea is using the local area network to collect data from users and conducting data compression to relieve communications; and [Ning et al. \(2018b\)](#) that presents a green and sustainable VNE framework for collaborative EC in wireless-optical broadband access networks.

6. Conclusions

EI refers to the analysis of data and development of solutions at the site where the data is generated. By doing this, intelligent

edges reduce latency, costs, and security risks, thus making the associated business more efficient. The main gap for these benefits to materialize lies in building highly-intelligent and resource-efficient systems realizing the vision of EI. This review approaches the study of how intelligence is related to edge computing from two distinct perspectives: intelligence as the mechanism to be deployed in the node itself (AI on edge), and intelligence as a technology to help used devices in new computing environments (AI for edge).

In this paper we have presented the main concepts of EI and an extensive review of possible approaches and technological solutions to implement the EI paradigm. In addition, we have discussed the challenges and the opportunities that this paradigm offers. The main conclusion to be drawn from these challenges is that, whatever the application to be deployed, the set of requirements must be weighted according to the actual constraints governing the environment and the objectives of the application, i.e.: Not only must the concepts developed in the figure ([Fig. 3](#)) be taken into account, but it is also essential to prioritize the key ones to optimize: latency, bandwidth, energy and cost, to achieve consistency between the architecture and the performance of the application itself.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Maria Arostegui, Cristina Regueiro, Ana I. Torre-Bastida and Juan Lopez de Armentia reports financial support was provided by European Commission.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgement

This work has received funding, in the context of TERMINET project, from the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant agreement ID: 957406.

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